

SYNERGISCHE ANALYSE DER BEZIEHUNGEN UND VERÄNDERUNGEN VON NATUR UND GESELLSCHAFT

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Kurzfassung: In diesem Artikel wird das Verhältnis „Mensch-Gesellschaft-Natur“ unter dem Gesichtspunkt der Synergie analysiert. Die Entwicklung der menschlichen Gesellschaft, die Wissenschaft und der technische Fortschritt haben die Einstellung der Menschen zur Natur verändert, und die systematische Bewegung der Natur wirkt sich negativ auf die Biosphärenschicht aus. In diesem Artikel gibt der Autor einen Überblick über die globale Bedeutung ökologischer Probleme, basierend auf verschiedenen wissenschaftlichen und journalistischen Materialien. Das heutige Verhältnis „Mensch-Gesellschaft-Natur“ wird aus philosophischer Perspektive erlernt.

Schlüsselwörter: Mensch, Gesellschaft, Natur, synergetisch, Biosphäre, Noosphäre, dissipativ, integrativ, Bifurkation, System, Energie, linear, nichtlinear, stabil, instabil, Kompensator.

SYNERGICAL ANALYSIS OF NATURE AND SOCIETY RELATIONSHIPS AND CHANGES

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Abstract: In this article, the relationship between "human-society-nature" is analyzed from the point of view of synergy. The development of human society, science and technical progress have changed the attitude of people to nature, and the systematic movement of nature has a negative impact on the biosphere layer. In this article, the author gives a summary of the global importance of ecological problems, based on various scientific and journalistic materials. Today's relationship between "man-society-nature" is learned from a philosophical perspective.

Keywords: Human, society, nature, synergetic, biosphere, noosphere, dissipative, integrative, bifurcation, system, energy, linear, non-linear, stable, unstable, compensator.

Nature and social relations has been exciting people since ancient times and have not lost their importance until today. When we study the evolution of a certain historical development, we realize that it is dominated by the scientific paradigms of that time. Nature and society are closely related to the development of humanity, and all branches of science have tried to understand this dialectical relationship in different ways. The nature of this explanation depends on the attitudes of the society. Indeed, human society is an inseparable part of nature. The biological factor played an important role in the life cycle of the human society, and it was considered that the

satisfaction of biological needs is directly related to nature. Nature is especially important in the development of society and in its life. The reason for this is that the observance of social rules is determined by the nature of the order. The development of human society has always been an object of study in philosophy, since it is closely related to nature. At all times, people have always been interested in the influence of self-esteem, the relationship of self-esteem to society, and the importance of these questions haven't been lost. One of the philosophical issues is the relationship between society and nature, it's development, how people relate to them in the past and now? It consists of important questions about how to be in the future. These questions have become one of the pressing issues of today. The reason is that today's world has many different characteristics and its own direction of development.

Starting from the second half of the last century, as a result of the development of the natural and political worlds, the possibility of knowing the world was opened up, which led to the integration of these sciences and the paradigms of understanding the world. Synergetic, a teaching aimed at understanding the new content of the digital world, has begun to be recognized as a method of scientific knowledge.

The word synergetic (Greek *sinergicos* - joint action) was introduced into science by the German physicist G. Hacken. Synergetics appeared as a main direction in the 60s and 70s of the 20th century. In this, G. Haken, G. Nikolis, A. Klimontovich's service was great. He tried to find the rules of direction in physical, chemical, biological events, as well as in economic, technical, and political processes, such as self-organization, self-management, transition from order to disorder, linear and non-linear [1].

In this case, through its regularity, synergetic acts to understand the rules of the society and nature, and the connections in the system are also related to each other. Synergetic appeared in the 21st century and created a new way of understanding the integration of sciences. Today's world has many different characteristics, and it requires a complex methodology to explain and understand. As such methodology, synergetic provides great opportunities for understanding nature, nature and society's interdependence. So, nature and society become a single system, and the system gives an open system, because the components of the given system are continuously connected, matter, energy, and information exchange between them, and it lives as a single system. Such a system will have a developing character. If we consider nature as an objective reality, society is a part of nature. It is in continuous relationship with society and nature, and it is preserved under the principle of the unity of nature and society (if we take the meaning of nature as nature). The role, place, and energy of the biosphere in the natural system is determined by the relationship of living organisms to each other and to inanimate nature, as well as the relationship of the people to nature. The biosphere takes into account the dialectical unity of animate and inanimate nature, as well as the habitat of living organisms and their influence on the habitat. Biosphere (bio... also Greek. *sphaira* - sphere) is the shell of the Earth's living organisms. In the composition of the biosphere, energetics of living organisms have played a main role. Biosphere (bio... also Greek. *sphaira* - sphere) is the shell of the Earth's living organisms.

The activity of living organisms plays a major role in the structure and energy of the biosphere. Lamarck first expressed the idea of the biosphere as the "direction of life", the outer shell of the Earth. The term "biosphere" was introduced into science by the Australian geologist E. Zuss (1875). The study of the biosphere was carried out by the Russian scientist V. I. Vernadsky (1926). Since nature is a complex system, the connections between the elements are diverse, and the elements themselves are composed of complex components. So, we can consider the biosphere as a nuclear part of a system that needs to be built by itself to maintain the integrity of the whole society.

Earth's biosphere appeared about 4.5 billion years ago. It has been developing as a self-sustaining system since before the beginning of humanity and until today. In the early stages of evolution, there was a certain amount of oxygen in the atmosphere, but it was gradually enriched with oxygen as a result of the appearance of plants with low photosynthetic ability. In turn, this served as a necessary condition for the development of numerous animal groups. This process affects the composition of the biosphere layer in the natural world. In the first phase of the development of the biosphere, there was a period of biogenesis, and in this period, the turnover of natural substances (substances) consisted of the reproduction of all living organisms. Later, the arrival of people started a new era in the development of the biosphere [2].

The emergence of humanity was connected with the biosphere layer, and it became part of the structure of the left process together with the effect of its self-development. Among the living creatures created by nature, man is unique. This unique feature was connected with the intellect and perceptive of a person, and brought him dominance when comparing him to other living beings in the biosphere. The intellectual side of the relationship between society and nature creates a noospheric stage of development. The noosphere is a new geological phenomenon of our planet. In this place, man becomes a huge geological phenomenon for the first time [3].

That is why, it is necessary to take responsibility for future development of nature. The development of society is inextricably linked with the environment. The biosphere will one day pass into the noosphere. A great union appeared, and as a result, the development of the planet was controlled by the force of intelligence! The simple explanation of the noosphere is the direction of intelligence. It was called the part of the biosphere's transformation under the influence of man. V. Vernadskyi stated several times that the joint development of society and nature requires the creation of special structures for the joint development of nature, responsibility for nature and the future of society, and the creation of special structures for joint development. Therefore, the noosphere is a state of the biosphere, and if its development is in accordance with the goal, the mind deserves to manage the development of the biosphere for the benefit of man and his future. For these reasons, I think it is appropriate to speak not about the noosphere, but about the noosphere period, when a person can manage with his own power and intelligence and can ensure such a connection with the environment, an environment that allows both the development of nature[4]. Despite the fact that the problem of the joint development

of the natural and human society was discussed in the last century, subjectivity has not been fully understood as the intermediate problem of the human society. Because of this, the layer biospheric shell, which represents the unity of nature and society, is disappearing.

The nature is dissipative (Lat. Dissipation-dissipation), a single dissipative system. Composite, multi-order, multi-variant, non-linear systems are called dissipative systems in synergetic. The system, which is made up of many interconnected parts, has increased the possibilities of independent integration. At the same time, such a system creates a non-linearity, a dissipative system, which includes evolutionary signs. A dissipative system not only absorbs energy, but also dissipates it. For example: Nature realizes its self-organization through the exchange of matter and energy of the system state, thus ensuring the mutual participation and connection between its components. The life expectancy of living organisms is related to the energy in the biosphere. According to Vernadiski, the biosphere includes all living and non-living things on our planet. The biosphere is a very open, unstable system that can only be sustained by solar energy [5].

It absorbs solar energy and supports biochemical processes on Earth. The emergence of the biosphere was connected with solar energy, which accelerated the evolutionary processes in it several times. It provides the process of development in living matter. Living matter is a complex system of living organisms, including plants, animals, and humans. The uniqueness of the biosphere is its diversity, self-control, and ability to thrive. This includes openness of the biosphere system to self-organization, energy exchange with the solar system, and the ability of living organisms to transform this energy into other energy. At the same time, the diversity of living organisms and their interactions maintain stability in the biosphere. In terms of size and weight, living matter is a small part of the biosphere, but people have a great power to change the appearance of our planet. Due to the small interaction of living organisms, it keeps the Earth in a state of balance, and affects the fertility of the soil as well as the climate. Self-organization has a compensatory character. If one part of the system fails to function, the remaining parts will try to replace it. Such a feature is also recognized in the system of nature and society. Currently, the biospheric feature of nature is disappearing. Of course, this happens as a result of anthropogenic influence. This biospheric function has been restored by the human society through technospheric and noospheric activity. Such work can prolong the life of the biosphere! We need to enrich the ecosphere with a strong ecosophic worldview. Otherwise, we will lose our current ecological situation. Nature has a compensatory quality and since childhood, people have a subjective relationship to the environment. This attitude creates an obstacle to the creation of the ecosphere.

Nature has been living until now as an integrative (lat. integratio- restore, fill,) system, but now nature is losing this characteristic. If we call nature as an objective reality, then in the objective reality, all the processes related to life and the self-organization of living organisms take place in the biosphere. Society, being a part of nature, has a special place in the self-organization of nature. Neither society nor nature can survive without exchange of matter and energy. Nature has been a source

of energy in all the stages of the development of human society. So, the relationship between society and nature played an important role. Integration serves to determine the self-maintenance mechanism, maintenance factors and complexity of the system. If the energy level of the parts exceeds the integrative energy level of the whole, the system collapses. At the same time, if the external energy limit exceeds the integrative energy of the system, the system will be destroyed. Nature may lose the possibility of self-organization in the future. The reason is that the energy trees in it are under threat from year to year, it is clear that the excessive influence of human activity leads to the loss of the ability of nature to restore itself. For example, in the first step of the development of the human society, he started to learn how to use firewood as a source of energy for cooking. At that time, energy sources were limited to what nature provided, and the strength of human muscles played the main role. The development of human entrepreneurship led to the creation of the wheel, the complexity of labor tools, and the development of production for the use of iron products led to an increase in the use of energy sources.

Over time, people used animals, water, wind energy, horses, and small amounts of coal, and compared to the people of the previous era, they became more and more powerful. The significant use of energy data is related to the emergence of industrialized countries. Indiscriminate use of energy sources has affected the loss of balance in nature. For example, according to various sources, energy consumption in the USA is 6 times higher than the global level and 30 times higher than in developing countries. If developing countries were to increase their production of mineral resources to the level of the United States, then the estimated reserves of oil would decrease after 7 years, natural gas after 5 years, and coal after 18 years. At the current growth rates of technology, after 240 years the energy production on Earth will increase from the amount of solar energy falling on our planet, after 800 years - from all the energy emitted by the Sun, and after 1300 years, the total radiation of our entire galaxy will increase. It is impossible for such a thing to happen, because nature itself forbids it. For this reason, it is necessary to reduce the pace of the economic growth that has been going on for a long time, it is necessary to develop a new, alternative way of humanity [6].

Homo sapiens, a biological species, does not have a place in the biosphere to this day, but considers the natural environment of the planet as a utilitarian supplement that satisfies its unlimited needs, therefore, by destroying the natural ecosystem of the earth, it continues to create an artificial environment (Technosphere) for itself. As V. I. Vernadsky said in the twenties century, humanity has turned into a huge geological mass and has begun to exert a noticeable influence on the planetary flows of both matter and energy. As a result, in the course of 4 billion years of evolution, the balance of the cyclical cycles that appeared on Earth was broken, which led to a global ecological crisis, in which the biosphere climate lost its ability to reliably maintain the stability of all chemical factors [7]. Despite such warnings, humanity's attitude towards nature has not changed! Of course, these confirmations are part of the bifurcation processes inherent in the emergence and development of human society, the disregard of natural laws, and the creation of a

technospheric society. In the case of bifurcation, it is observed that two or more elements are dispersed into various forms because of opposition. The reason is that when the orderliness and stability in the system is removed, it turns into chaos. This is due to the nature of the processes that are presented, and the reason for this is the system of self-completion. Main features of self-complementary system are instability and nonlinearity. This knowledge explains the mechanism of the emergence of disorder. When the system is in the state of thermodynamic equilibrium, all its elements act independently of each other and it is not worthy to form ordered structures. (at times) the movements of the open system remained unclear. The process was called the bifurcation (branching) of an unclear point. At the point of bifurcation, the role of these influences on the system changes: the influence of the system is significant and leads to unforeseeable consequences. After passing the bifurcation point, the development of the system could not be predicted. The future of a system without an open balance cannot be predicted. Quantitative factors play an important role in the processes of self- development [8].

Nature is a self-perpetuating composite system. Such built-in systems have a multi-variant development character. The area surrounding the system was not strictly defined. Obstacles and opportunities will be opened. A characteristic sign of a linear system and not a linear system is that it is - the number of states, the number of possibilities for development. The number of such cases, the quality of the change is determined by the properties of the system itself. If... the bifurcation point is far away, the system has only one-digit changes, and the quality of the system does not change. However, at the point of bifurcation, as a result of the low back effect, the properties of the system change in a cardinal way. That is, the concept of non-linearity describes the conditions that correspond to the nature of a complex system, such aspects of complexity - multivariability, irreversibility of the process, the inability to unambiguously state the next states of the processes, chaos, alternative ways of development, and the principle of superposition in such a system. "non-linear", i.e. "a small external influence on a non-linear system can have a very large effect" [9].

Today, nature is at the point of bifurcation. Biological diversity is disappearing and climate change is approaching an irreversible level. At present, climate change is occurring in all parts of our planet, and the duration of the hot season is increasing. If the global warming on our planet increases every year, it will affect all aspects of our society. In 2020, the average global temperature is expected to increase by 1.2 degrees compared to the period of 1850-1900, and by 2024, it is likely to decrease by 1.5 degrees. According to the report of the World Metrology Institute, the water temperature in the oceans has dropped to a record level. This year's "heat wave" was observed in the region of 80%. Global warming is not only a increase in temperature, but also an increase in the acidity of the ocean, because the ocean is releasing a large amount of carbon dioxide. This causes great damage to the marine ecosystem[10].

It has been said that the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is increasing, despite the coronavirus pandemic, quarantine-related changes, the increase in industrial production, and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

There are two possibilities in the case of development at the bifurcation point of the system. One of them is the rule of thumb, it is possible to monitor the progress of the processes, and the second is to control the processes and take a purposeful action [11]. Therefore, humanity requires a responsible approach to society and nature. Due to the bifurcation of the biosphere, the inexorable influence of the human society on nature has led to the end of humanity! "That's why, the outcome of our actions would not affect the continuity of the world[12].

In today's situation of humanity, it is necessary for everyone to take care of it. It is necessary to take drastic measures at the global level in order not to allow such a process. It is certain that we will not change our lives with such stereotypes of the society, with the rapid development of technological civilization in the last century. In the 21st century, technology, ideology, morals, and humanistic ideas seem to be giving up on familiar things. Perhaps the 21st century will go down in history as the beginning of the "Great Rejection" period [13].

There is no doubt that there is a certain level of rationality in these thoughts. Today, humanity demands a change in its approach to nature. Now, humanity is trying to improve the natural order of society. Of course, in this, the scientific system is replaced by the satisfaction of the requirements through the development of technology. In such a society, science, technology, and information are valued. Today, one of the ways to preserve our nature is the development of science and technology you can solve the problem by looking at the ways, therefore, our paying more attention to subjective factors is also related to molding the ecological, ethical, aesthetic world-view in the subjective mind. Academician N.N.Moiseev, the more we try to master nature, the more we depend on it. After all, the material of all modern goods is obtained from natural environment. For the left reason, the problems could not be solved by technical rules alone. The development of sensory unity with nature in the foundation of human technology requires the rapid development of society's culture, the reconstruction of humanitarian qualities [14].

The development of science and technology demands more and more from us, but despite the fact that our age is superior to all other ages in terms of knowledge, I would like to announce that it is necessary to achieve great wisdom, humanity, morality, and courtesy[15].

During the research, in the context of synergetics, what will give confidence in the understanding of the interaction of "nature and society"? We found an answer to the question.

Firstly, "nature-society" gives a constructive system, an open system. Both linear and non-linear systems consist of a dialectical unity, and this unity is written in the context of the biosphere.

Secondly, nature is a large complex self-organizing ecosystem. The stability of nature depends on the diversity of living organisms in the biosphere. The working elements of the system perform various functions and provide energy. This feature comes from the coevolution of biogenic and abiogenic processes. Humanity is an integral part of ecosystems.

Therefore, our nature today is full of bifurcations, and at the point of bifurcation, it is possible to cause chaos in nature with a small impact. At the point of bifurcation, the development of the system could not be predicted in advance, and its development had many variants. The human society started with the rapid selection of coevolutionary development in nature. We call this an attractor in synergetics. At the same time, the society is developing under the influence of natural fluctuations.

Fourthly, over time, the development of the intellectual activity of humanity has changed the attitude towards nature. Such a relationship led to the loss of the ability of the biosphere to grow crops on its own, starting from the middle of the 20th century. Humanity cannot survive without the biosphere. It is an axiom that the self-improvement of the human society has been prevented by nature, and the simultaneous co-evolution of society and nature cannot be achieved. How can we ensure the joint development of nature and society today? While taking the moral principles as a priority, and introducing some forms into the work of the people.

References.

1. Falsafa qiskacha isohli lugat Toshkent - 2004 284 p.
2. Z.M. Sattorov Ecology "Sano-standart" publishing house Tashkent - 2018-25p.
3. V.I.Vernadsky Biosphere and noosphere Moscow 149-c "NAUKA" 1989
4. Moiseev H. H. \ Man and noosphere. — M.: Mol. guard, 1990. 24-c
5. [<http://www.aspirantfilosov.narod.ru/1-26.html> Problems of the biosphere and ecology in modern science. Philosophy of Russian cosmism and the doctrine of VI. Vernadsky on the biosphere, technosphere and noosphere]
6. Berdimuratova A.K., Mukhammadiyarova A. Philosophy of ecological safety, p. 30, Nokis, "Karakalpakstan»2012
7. {<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/predstavleniya-cheloveka-o-prirodnoy-srede-i-filosofskiy-aspekt-preodoleniya-mirovogo-ekologicheskogo-krizisa>} { Tkachenko Yury Leonidovich, Komissarova Maria Viktorovna, Shved Margarita Alexandrovna Human perspectives of the natural environment and the philosophical aspect of overcoming the world environmental crisis }
8. [https://studref.com/359630/ekonomika/sinergeticheskiy_podhod_poznaniyu_okr_uzhayuschego_mira «Синергетический подход к познанию окружающего мира»
9. Newsletter of Korakalpok State University named after Berdak. No. 3 (36) 2017 95-b some methodological issues of complexity research. Niyazimbetov M. Ts. National University of Uzbekistan
10. <https://news.un.org/ru/story/2020/12/1391602> [WMO: By 2024, global temperatures could exceed pre-industrial levels by 1.5 degrees]
11. Vestnik KGU im. Berdakha. No. 2 (51) 2021. New Uzbekistan as a new social reality: philosophical-synergistic analysis Orazbaev A.K. Karakalpak State University
12. [<https://ru.unesco.org/courier/2019-3/filosofskie-i-eticheskie-aspekty-izmeneniya-klimata>] Philosophical and ethical aspects of climate change

13. [S.P., Kurdyumov S.P., Malinetsky G.G. synergy and future forecasts].<http://urss.ru/cgi-bin/db.pl?cp=&page=Book&id=241192&lang=Ru&blang=ru&list=Found>]

14. https://knowledge.allbest.ru/ecology/2c0b65625b3bc79a4c43a88421306d37_1.html socio-philosophical aspects of the ecological crisis

15. Danilo Zh. Markovich social ecology Moscow 1997 p-7